

Explore

Group

Case Processing Summary

Group	Valid	Cases		Total			
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
SmlArena	Beacon	5	100.0%	0	0.0%	5	100.0%
	Random	15	100.0%	0	0.0%	15	100.0%
MedArena	Beacon	5	100.0%	0	0.0%	5	100.0%
	Random	15	100.0%	0	0.0%	15	100.0%
LrgArena	Beacon	5	100.0%	0	0.0%	5	100.0%
	Random	15	100.0%	0	0.0%	15	100.0%

Descriptives

Group	Statistic	Std. Error		
SmlArena	Beacon	Mean	42.820	3.8592
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	32.105	
		Upper Bound	53.535	
	5% Trimmed Mean	42.733		
	Median	41.600		
	Variance	74.467		
	Std. Deviation	8.6294		
	Minimum	32.9		
	Maximum	54.3		
	Range	21.4		
	Interquartile Range	16.4		
	Skewness	.325	.913	
	Kurtosis	-1.406	2.000	
	Random	Mean	52.687	11.9539
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	27.048	
		Upper Bound	78.325	
5% Trimmed Mean		46.569		
Median		42.100		
Variance		2143.420		
Std. Deviation		46.2971		
Minimum		14.4		
Maximum		201.1		
Range		186.7		
Interquartile Range		32.3		
Skewness		2.613	.580	
Kurtosis		8.025	1.121	
MedArena		Beacon	Mean	86.660

Descriptives

Group			Statistic	Std. Error
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	57.651	
		Upper Bound	115.669	
	5% Trimmed Mean	86.383		
	Median	72.500		
	Variance	545.823		
	Std. Deviation	23.3629		
	Minimum	64.4		
	Maximum	113.9		
	Range	49.5		
	Interquartile Range	43.5		
	Skewness	.530	.913	
	Kurtosis	-3.077	2.000	
	Random	Mean	112.793	22.7600
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	63.978	
Upper Bound		161.609		
5% Trimmed Mean	107.237			
Median	77.000			
Variance	7770.268			
Std. Deviation	88.1491			
Minimum	21.9			
Maximum	303.7			
Range	281.8			
Interquartile Range	100.5			
Skewness	1.306	.580		
Kurtosis	.889	1.121		
LrgArena	Beacon	Mean	129.440	10.2268
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	101.046
		Upper Bound	157.834	
	5% Trimmed Mean	129.061		
	Median	120.300		
	Variance	522.933		
	Std. Deviation	22.8677		
	Minimum	106.1		
	Maximum	159.6		
	Range	53.5		
	Interquartile Range	43.3		
	Skewness	.553	.913	
	Kurtosis	-2.115	2.000	
	Random	Mean	180.007	26.9118
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	122.287	
		Upper Bound	237.727	
5% Trimmed Mean		174.452		
Median	156.600			

Descriptives

Group		Statistic	Std. Error
	Variance	10863.665	
	Std. Deviation	104.2289	
	Minimum	37.1	
	Maximum	422.9	
	Range	385.8	
	Interquartile Range	136.7	
	Skewness	.816	.580
	Kurtosis	.523	1.121

Tests of Normality

	Group	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
SmlArena	Beacon	.156	5	.200*	.970	5	.876
	Random	.282	15	.002	.700	15	<.001
MedArena	Beacon	.328	5	.084	.806	5	.091
	Random	.240	15	.020	.838	15	.012
LrgArena	Beacon	.255	5	.200*	.908	5	.453
	Random	.140	15	.200*	.949	15	.509

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

SmlArena

Stem-and-Leaf Plots

SmlArena Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Group= Beacon

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Frequency   Stem & Leaf
          2.00   3 . 25
          2.00   4 . 18
          1.00   5 . 4
    
```

Stem width: 10.0
Each leaf: 1 case(s)

SmlArena Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Group= Random

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Frequency   Stem & Leaf
          1.00   0 . 1
          6.00   0 . 222233
          5.00   0 . 44555
    
```

.00 0.
2.00 0.88
1.00 Extremes (>=201)

Stem width: 100
Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plots

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plots

MedArena

Stem-and-Leaf Plots

MedArena Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Group= Beacon

Frequency	Stem & Leaf
3.00	0 . 677
2.00	1 . 11

Stem width: 100.0
Each leaf: 1 case(s)

MedArena Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Group= Random

Frequency	Stem & Leaf
3.00	0 . 223
6.00	0 . 567778
2.00	1 . 12
2.00	1 . 59
2.00	Extremes (>=291)

Stem width: 100.0
Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plots

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plots

LrgArena

Stem-and-Leaf Plots

LrgArena Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Group= Beacon

Frequency	Stem & Leaf
4.00	1 . 0124
1.00	1 . 5

Stem width: 100.0
Each leaf: 1 case(s)

LrgArena Stem-and-Leaf Plot for
Group= Random

Frequency	Stem & Leaf
3.00	0 . 368
6.00	1 . 011459
4.00	2 . 1347
1.00	3 . 0
1.00	4 . 2

Stem width: 100.0
Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plots

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plots

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of LrgArena

for Group= Beacon

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of LrgArena

for Group= Random

